

REMEDIATING LITERACY GAPS OF GRADE 6 LEARNERS IN SCIENCE INSTRUCTION: A CONTEXTUALIZED LEARNING KIT

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Remediating Literacy Gaps of Grade 6 Learners in Science Instruction: A Contextualized Learning Kit

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Abstract

The study remediates the literacy gaps of the Grade 6 learners using the Contextualized Learning Kit (CLK) focusing the Word Recognition and Reading Comprehension to the selected public elementary schools in Cluster 1 of Carcar City Division during School Year 2023-2024. The study utilized the parallel research design employing the purposive sampling technique with forty (40) participants who were identified as Frustration and Instructional Level based on the Phil-IRI Group Screening Test. This research used the standardized Graded passage with 7-item test to assess the proficiency levels of the participants through pre-and post-assessment. The findings exhibited the following results, the Experimental Group have manifested the “improved” remark in word recognition with a weighted mean of 90.427, standard deviation of 5.792, and success rate of 55 percent and in reading comprehension with a weighted mean of 64.286, standard deviation of 13.513, and success rate of 50 percent, in contrary, the scores of Controlled Group have “remained” remark in word recognition with a weighted mean of 92.985, standard deviation of 1.673, and success rate of 25 percent and reading comprehension with a weighted mean of 78.571, standard deviation of 15.019, and success rate of 50 percent. The result recommended a thorough implementation of CLK in school since this is a great tool in developing the interest of the selected pupils while mastering the recognition and comprehension skills for the Phil-IRI assessment.

Keywords: *contextualized learning kit, literacy gaps, grade 6 learners*

Introduction

In today’s teaching schema, teachers are in close supervision on the learning gaps of the learners in the public elementary schools. Teachers are very much aware of the learning crisis experienced by the learners in school particularly on the word recognition and reading comprehension skills. These skills are essential for learning development and academic performance of the learners along the impact in learning and understanding the subject. Reading is part of the developmental skill towards other academic skills, it is prerequisite in the academic skills. Meanwhile, students who cannot read fluently the text will not enroll in other topics. Therefore, reading fluently is essential to a student’s success in the classroom and even in later life. If student is not engaged in literacy exercises, they won’t be able to enhance their scientific literacy. However, in order to raise their science literacy, learners must improve their reading ability to understand scientific concepts which poses a significant obstacle in all students.

One of the crucial elements, maybe considering students’ areas of weaknesses and employing the best teaching strategy for their requirements and preferences. In order to improve pupils’ reading comprehension, a variety of reading resources maybe quite helpful. Not all methods, nevertheless, are appropriate or helpful to all learners (James et al., 2020). Teachers who use excellent inferential comprehension questions can help learners become more aware of underused approaches and focus their attention to underutilized powerful strategies. The lack of knowledge with “the two new” approaches on teaching pupils and teachers how to respond to reading comprehension questions. Through such more exercises in the syllabus, for instance, the use of changes and logical comprehension methods may produce the best result. Pupils lack of familiarity with the studies strategies, or the “the two new” strategies, in responding to and teaching reading comprehension questions for pupils and teachers, respectively. For instance, adding additional tasks to syllabus and using rearrangement and inferential comprehension approaches may produce the best result. There are two types of reading instructions in the Philippines: the regular reading class in which it is part of the core curriculum, and the remedial reading class in which it is a separate subject offered to the students who need further assistance in improving the reading skill due to difficulties. Since it is not included in the students’ regular reading class, the remedial reading class in the Philippines is a pull-out type (Umali, 2016).

Likewise, that Philippines educational system still does not recognize this position as a professional one in the classroom. There are currently no budgetary allocations for positions that aid and support to kids who struggle with reading. Therefore, in contrast to the respect shown to this profession in the US and other foreign nations, teaching remedial reading is seen as an additional workload for instructors who are not paid for performing the roles and obligations entrusted to them. Additionally, the requirements for teachers of remedial reading are not really specific and obvious. In fact, local schools typically have the classroom reading teachers simultaneously serve as the remedial reading teachers for kids who have been identified as having reading issues. Despite offering remedial reading, DepEd lacks consistent on coordinated criteria for remedial reading instruction (Rio, 2017). Hence, being a remedial reading teacher is considered an extra workload for teachers and is not compensated for doing roles and responsibilities entrusted to them as opposed to the recognition given to this job in the US and other foreign countries. Not only this, but the qualifications of remedial reading should also be done in schools (Batan, 2016).

With the numerous anecdotal reports, teachers’ observations, and the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) tallied, the science teacher decided to assess and unravel the word recognition and reading comprehension skills of the learners in the three (3) elementary schools of

cluster 1, the Kalangyawon Elementary School, Puesto Elementary School, and Kayam Elementary School using the Phil-IRI result, assessment catalogue, and contextualize learning kit to address the learning crisis of the students in learning the science subject. Likewise, the science teacher will try to find ways to meet the needs of all the learners, most especially those learners who have different learning and thinking differences. Moreover, to find-out the reading proficiency level of the learners, the science teacher will use a diagnostic tool to identify the reading literacy level of the learners by pre-reading assessment using simple science words in science competencies. This tool is used to assess a learner’s comprehension in reading. This diagnostic assessment will assess the learner’s reading capability and track their level of proficiency.

Thus, this study aimed to generate information about the word recognition and reading comprehension of the learners in order to address the learning crisis that the Grade 6 learners. The findings of this study served as basis for the development of a strategic instructional model which will guide the public-school teachers and school administrators in designing appropriate interventions to address issues and concerns relative to the motivational orientation of the learners and their academic achievement in science in terms of their preferred modality. The aforementioned modalities are considered alternative continuity learning platforms which will be utilized during cancellation of classes.

Research Questions

This research assessed the effectiveness of Contextualized Learning Kit (CLK) in remediating the literacy gaps of Grade 6 learners in word recognition and reading comprehension among public elementary schools of Cluster 1, Carcar City Division during school year 2023-2024, as basis for the development of intervention plan. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the pre-assessment proficiency level of the controlled group and experimental group in terms of:
 - 1.1. word recognition, and
 - 1.2. reading comprehension?
2. What is the post-assessment proficiency level of the controlled group and experimental group in terms of:
 - 2.1. word recognition, and
 - 2.2. reading comprehension?
3. What are the comparative results between the pre-assessment and post-assessment of proficiency level of the experimental group and controlled group in word recognition and in reading comprehension?
4. Based on the findings, what science contextualized learning kit will be designed?

Methodology

Research Design

This research study employed the quantitative research design in parallel method to assess the proficiency level of the Grade 6 learners while using the Contextualize Learning Kit. The parallel method will be used in the first part focusing on the chosen group, the control group and experimental group, to evaluate the results of these two groups, and the final part administering the treatment based on the first part’s findings before coming to a decision. Hence, such design is used to test the difference of the pre-assessment and post-assessment results of the two groups, control, and experimental groups, on word recognition and reading comprehension after the treatment. According to McGrew (2001), parallel research design is a method where two or more groups are given treatment unique from each other. Typically, the participants in a group are randomly done.

Participants

The participants of this study were forty (40) official enrollees in the Grade 6 level from the three (3) elementary schools of Cluster 1, Carcar City Division, with literacy challenges particularly on word recognition and reading comprehension. They were identified based on the Phil-IRI Group Screening Test results administered in the First Quarter assessment of the School Year 2023-2024. Purposive sampling technique was utilized in this study. According to Dornyei (2007), purposeful sampling is a technique to find individuals who can provide rich and varied insights into the phenomenon under investigation. Furthermore, it is a technique in which the person initiating the research relies on their perception to purposively choose the participants of their study.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Participants*

Cluster 1 Schools	Participants Proficiency Level on Phil-IRI Parameters	Frequency of the Participant by Gender				Total	
		Male		Female		f	%
		f	%	f	%		
Kalangyawon ES	Frustration	5	12.50	2	5.00	7	17.50
	Instructional	6	15.00	2	5.00	8	20.00
Kayam ES	Frustration	6	15.00	4	10.00	10	25.00
	Instructional	4	10.00	5	12.50	9	22.50
Puesto ES	Frustration	1	2.50	2	5.00	3	7.50
	Instructional	1	2.50	2	5.00	3	7.50
Total		23	57.50	17	42.50	40	100.00

Table 1 portrays the basic information on the reading ability of Grade 6 learners in the three public schools. It is noted in the total tally that 12 males and eight females are identified as frustration readers while 11 males and nine females are instructional. This means that 30% of the 40 learners with reading difficulties are males and 20% are females categorized as frustration readers. On the other hand, 27.5% are males and 22.5% are females, categorized as instructional readers. The basis for interpreting the individual reading profile of the participants from the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil- IRI) included the criteria for word recognition: 97-100 is independent readers, 90-96 are instructional readers, and 89 below are frustration readers. For reading comprehension the criteria are: 80-100 considered independent, 59-79 are instructional readers, and 58 below are frustration readers. Instructional reader needs the support of the teacher or parent. This is the level in which new vocabulary and concepts are introduced and where the greatest progress in reading occurs. Using text at a learner's instructional level is ideal for guided reading groups. Frustration reader finds it difficult to decode words, identify vocabulary words and concepts. For them to be guided, the teacher needs to read the text to them so they can be exposed to high level vocabulary (Department of Education, 2018).

Instruments

This study utilized and adopted the standardized Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) tool from the 2018 Manual, First Edition published by the Department of Education (DepEd) under the leadership of Secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones (2018). Furthermore, the participants of the study were examined based on the Phil-IRI Group Screening Test (GST) to determine the oral reading, silent reading comprehension, and listening comprehension levels within their grade level. Consequently, the participants were verified through a graded passage entitled "The Chameleons" with eighty-two (82) words and seven (7) item test.

On the other hand, the participants undergone the three (3) formative stages in the Contextualized Learning Kit (CLK). This is done to establish and check the word recognition and reading comprehension skills of the participants related to the context of Science Instruction.

Procedure

The data gathering of this study was satisfied by three phases namely pre-data collection, actual data collection, and post data collection.

Pre-Data Collection. Prior to the conduct of study, the researcher asked the approval of the Dean of the Graduate School of Education, University of the Visayas. After the Dean nodded his consent, permission was sought from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent on the aim of conducting research in the Division of Car-car City. Upon approval by Schools Division Superintendent, another letter request was sent to the School Head requesting permission from them for the participation of Grade 6 learners in the study. After the design hearing, the observations and corrections of the panel members were incorporated and subsequently the manuscript was submitted to the Research Ethics Committee (REC) for review. Upon securing a notice to proceed by the REC, the data collection commenced.

Actual Data Collection. During the administration of the post-assessment tool, a brief discussion on the content and purpose of the study was introduced to the School Heads and classroom advisers for them to be oriented with the agenda of the study. The data for the pre-assessment results were taken from the Enhanced Management Information System (EMIS) of the school. The pre-assessment in English was administered to all Grade 4 and 6 learners within the first quarter of the school year through the Phil-IRI Group Screening Test (Department of Education, 2018). The post-assessment was done in the second quarter of the school year. The identified 40 learners with reading difficulties were equally divided into two groups, control group and experimental group. The participants for each group were randomly selected from the 40 learners with reading difficulties. Each group was placed in a classroom respectively. Simultaneous administration of the test was done for both groups. The control group was made to answer the test which content did not bear context clues and picture clues while the experimental group answered the test with those clues. Both groups answered their respective test in silent oral reading, which means no teacher guided them to read.

Post Data Collection. The pre and post assessment results were organized and analyzed using the appropriate statistical tool. The data were carefully handled with utmost confidentiality and in no case would ever be made open to the public. For keep safe the collected, the same shall be encoded on the google drive such that only the research can access the data. It is also assured that after the approval and printing of the manuscript, all data will be completely destroyed.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used to analyze and interpret the data:

Frequency. This formula is used to accurately determine the number of participants and raw scores from the pre-and post-assessment results including the Formative Assessments in the Contextualized Learning Kit (CLK).

Percentage. This formula is used to proportion the number of participants and validate the scores of the participants in the Phil-IRI standards on Proficiency Level.

Weighted Mean. This formula is used to make a clear analysis and consistent estimates on the gathered data based on the variables of the study such as the pre-and post-assessments of Word Recognition and Reading Comprehension.

Standard Deviation. This formula is used to gauge the scatteredness of the raw scores based on the weighted mean of the study. Through this, it provides evidence on how concentrated the gathered data of the study.

Fisher's Exact Test. This formula is used to test the independence between pre- and post-assessment results on Word Recognition and Reading Comprehension in both Experimental and Controlled group.

Ethical Considerations

This study underwent careful planning and conduct including the ethical and ethical requirements. The study employed numerous stages to resolve some ethical issues and concerns related to procedure and manner in collecting data from the respondents by taking into consideration the privacy and confidentiality of their responses.

Protection of Human Rights. Protecting the rights of the respondents involved in this research is a vital concern of the researcher. As such, the following aspects were observed to protect the rights of the participants.

Beneficence. This study followed the principle of beneficence that minimizes harm to the research respondents and the research community. Additionally, this investigation maximizes benefits specifically in the collection of needed data. This research is beneficial to the school heads, teachers, stakeholders, and the entire school community.

Respect. This study ensured human dignity and respect in all forms of races, religion practices, self-determination of participants and their right to full disclosure. Their responses were respected and kept with utmost confidentiality. The results of the study placed no one in a disadvantageous situation. This was highly voluntary and in no case the respondents were forced to participate.

Justice. The researcher dealt with all the respondents with fair and just treatment. No one is being treated special nor better than the other. The researcher shows respect to the idea that all participants in the Cluster 1 of Car-car Division are treated equitably and their right to privacy is paramount.

Transparency. To practice transparency in this research, the researcher understood how to implement and conduct this study in the most honest way. To achieve transparency, the researcher presented all the activities, documentary requirements and observe prior approval of all communications before commencing to the actual data gathering. The researcher maintains open communication and full accountability in this research process and presents the result of the study to the participants for information dissemination.

Risk-Benefit Assessment. The study was being designed to determine the reading proficiency level in Science of Grade 6 learners in the. Careful and well-planned process and analysis of data to protect the interest of the participants from discomfort, biases, threat, and other disadvantages relative to the subjects of the study.

Benefits. With just and honest responses from the participants on this study, the following benefits were beneficial to all stakeholders in the public schools: (1) it aids the school officials design appropriate intervention to increase the performance of the learners, (2) it helps the school authorities determine the appropriate learning modality suited to the interest of the learners; and (3) provide the necessary data for decision-making and development of localized policy.

Risks. The researcher paid due consideration to the preservation and protection of the respondents' rights and confidentiality. There are minimal risks associated with this study in terms of their time consumed in answering the survey questionnaire. The researcher guaranteed their backgrounds are preserved appropriately. The participants were assured that participating in this study could not give any harm to them and to the institution. Also, they are informed that the data gathered from their responses will be used for research and academic purposes only. And the nature of their commitment to participate and answer the research tool is purely voluntary and that they have the right to decline and even delay in answering the tool if deemed necessary. Additionally, they are informed that their right to withdraw and withhold information will be respected. Failure to volunteer will not yield any undesirable effect to their employment in the government service.

Content, Comprehension and Documentation of Informed Consent. To protect the rights of the participants in this study, an informed consent form indicating approval by the REC was given to the participants together with the discussion on the purpose of the study. To ensure that the participation in the study was completely voluntary, an agreement executed by the researcher and the participants in the consent form by affixing their respective signatures on the instrument. The following were the provisions provided in the consent form:

Participant Status. The researcher assured the participants that the data collected will be for research and academic purposes only and in case shall be disclosed to the public and that their participation shall not cause prejudice to their employment and services to the public.

Study Goals. The study aimed to determine the proficiency level of Grade 6 Science learners in Cluster 1, Carcar City Division this school year 2022-2023 as the basis for contextualized learning kit remediation.

Type of Data. The quantitative data were collected using the pre-test and post test results. The gathered data were treated with appropriate statistical tools to address the statement of the problem and its subproblems.

Procedures. Once the permission from the Schools Division Superintendent was sought, the researcher administered the survey

questionnaires to the participants for them to answer. The data are carefully managed and interpreted swiftly. Ethical considerations are strictly observed to safeguard the interest of the respondents.

Nature of the Commitment. To ensure commitment by the participants, the researcher notified the former seeking time for an appointment in answering the questionnaire. Prior to answering the tool, the researcher observed ample time of orientation with the participants on the contents of the questionnaire for them to understand the purpose of the study.

Sponsorship. The study was part of an academic requirement and all expenses incurred were taken from the personal fund by the researcher.

Participant Selection. The participants of the study were the Grade 6 science learners' school in Cluster 1, Carcar City Division. The researcher employed a complete enumeration technique for this study.

Potential Risks. There were minimal risks associated with this study in terms of economic, social, psychological, physical, and emotional aspects. Furthermore, the reading materials were prepared through hard copy for selected participants. For social aspects, they were encouraged that this could be a great help to the researcher to read books as their habit.

Potential Benefits. In actively joining for the said study, the participants were made to understand the agenda and the benefits of the study to them and more on the interest in reading.

Alternatives. In the event the participants miss reading, the tool for whatever reason the researcher asked them to meet again at their most convenient time.

Compensation. There was no compensation given to the participants nor costs associated with their participation in the conduct of this study. No present is being given to them but a simple and sincere expression of gratitude.

Confidentiality Pledge. The researcher gave due consideration to the preservation and protection of the participants' rights and confidentiality. To protect the privacy of the respondents, anonymity of their identity was guaranteed. Only code was used if needed. Once the data were gathered, the same are to be kept with utmost confidentiality and in no case shall be disclosed to undesirable individuals.

Voluntary Consent. Answering the research tools was made voluntary and no amount of coercion was being applied. Participants' consent form was signed by them prior to giving the responses.

Right to Withdraw and Withhold Information. Participants were informed that they can withhold information if they wish to and withdraw from participation if they like too anytime. Failure to volunteer will not entail any penalty or loss of benefits.

Contact information. The contact number of the researcher was being stated in the consent form. The researcher also provided the contact information of University of the Visayas – CEB to the participants if ever they have questions, comments, or complaints regarding the conduct of the study specifically on the gathering of data.

Authorization to access private information. In the conduct of the study, no private or sensitive information was collected from the respondents. The researcher only gathered answers from the research questionnaire. Hence, the respondents were not obliged to give personal information, nor the researcher had no authority to access the private information of the participants.

Confidentiality Procedure. Anyone who participates in a study had an appropriate belief that the researcher will handle any data they give him or her with secrecy. As a consequence, those who participate have a right to anticipate that the information collected will remain private. The researcher is in charge of maintaining records. Those who responded were made aware that every data will be handled with respect and care and will remain confidential. However, in order to adhere to the confidentiality and conformance spelled forth in the informed permission, the information may only be disclosed in research publications or presentations with their consent. Since these instruments are only to be used for research, they must be shredded and buried after usage.

Debriefing, Communications, and Referrals. Before the actual data gathering, the participants are informed ahead through a communication subject to division's approval and wide dissemination to be integrated during the school heads meeting. Prior to the actual answering of the tool, the researcher explained to the participants the objectives or purposes of the study and its direction through an electronic mail. They are also informed that any information provided to be utilized for academic purposes only and even be gauged to provide various programs and interventions in the division and not on personal aspects of the respondents and that their own personal performances and school will not be put to a bad light. For update, the researcher will conduct a call to the school heads only based on the principal or school heads' convenient time.

Incentives or Compensation. In this study, the researcher was the owner of the work. While this study is purposely for the academic requirement only and conducted personally by the researcher, it is affirmed that there is no monetary compensation given to the respondents. The researcher financed all expenses incurred for this study.

Conflict of Interest. The researcher declared no conflict of interest to the study and the respondents since the researcher hired an enumerator who is a teacher and a researcher to help the researcher gather the data needed.

Collaborative Study Terms of Reference. An agreement was being executed by participants and the researcher for any utilization or publication of the study. In the same manner, the researcher also acknowledged the efforts of those who helped her complete the study.

Research Ethics Committee" (REC). Refers to an impartial committee that is designated to examine participant-involved research and determine the study's ethicality.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the study to answer the established research problems. The data are detailed in tabular forms with its narrative interpretation and analysis. The discussion of each table included the implications and supported by related literature or studies.

Pre-assessment on Phil-IRI Proficiency Level

The pre-assessment was administered in the first quarter of the school year through the Phil-IRI Group Screening Test (GST). This assessment was done to assess the oral reading ability and reading comprehension of the participants in the elementary level. The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) is an informal reading inventory used by the Department of Education (DepEd) composed of graded passages to determine the student's performance in oral reading and reading comprehension. It used as a classroom-based assessment tool which measures and interprets learner's reading performance in both English and Filipino languages (Department of Education, 2018). The results will also determine the proficiency level of the learners in word recognition and reading comprehension based on the given parameters on the manual.

Table 2. Pre-assessment Results on Word Recognition

<i>Test Group</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Proficiency Level</i>
Experimental	82.371	3.847	Frustration
Controlled	92.985	1.673	Instructional

Note: n=40. Proficiency Level: 89 and below Frustration; 90-96 Instructional; 97-100 Independent.

Table 2 presents the pre-assessment result of both Experimental and Control groups on Word Recognition. Moreover, the Table 2 explicitly shows the result in contrast to each test group in which the Experimental group has the mean of 82.371 with a standard deviation of 3.847 that made the group belonged to the Frustration Level while the Controlled group has the mean of 92.985 with a standard deviation of 1.673 that made the group belonged to the Instructional Level based on the parameters of Phil-IRI tool.

Furthermore, the data conveys that there was deficient performance of the participants in the Word Recognition with twenty (20) participants got the Frustration Level in the Experimental Group and twenty (20) participants got the Instructional Level in the Controlled group.

Manning, J., & Kunkel, A. (2014) stated that frustration readers find it difficult to decode words, identify vocabulary words, and concepts. He also added that for the learners to learn, the concerned teacher needs to read the text to them so they can be exposed to high level vocabulary.

Table 3. Pre-assessment Results on Reading Comprehension

<i>Test Group</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Proficiency Level</i>
Experimental	26.429	11.610	Frustration
Controlled	67.143	14.730	Instructional

Note: n=40. Proficiency Level: 89 and below Frustration; 90-96 Instructional; 97-100 Independent.

Table 3 presents the pre-assessment result on Reading Comprehension for both Experimental and Controlled groups. The Table 3 reveals the comparison of the two (2) test groups providing the mean, standard deviation, and proficiency level based on the parameters of Phil-IRI tool. Looking closely at the table, the Experimental Group has a mean of 26.429 with a standard deviation of 11.610 which made the group belong to the Frustration Level while the Controlled group has a mean of 67.143 with a standard deviation of 14.730 which made the group belonged to the Instructional Level based on the Reading Parameters of Phil-IRI.

This indicates that participants in the two (2) test groups have encountered struggles in the Reading Comprehension based on the provided passage and test items of the Phil-IRI tool. The groups' scores are interpreted as most likely higher in dispersion with high variance of dataset with twenty (20) participants is in Frustration Level in the Experimental group while the Controlled group has variation of parameters as follows: five (5) of which are Independent; eight (8) of which are Instructional; and seven (7) of which are Frustration. Indeed, reading comprehension is considered a valuable skill in developing a good learner since it provides clear instructions on events, issues, context, and information. With these, participants must have the mastery in comprehending and articulating the thrown issues based on the passage given.

Mila & Avila (2018) detailed that deficiencies in reading comprehension hinder students learning, resulting in lower academic performance that is derived among other things, from the difficulty to analyze and understand texts. Comprehension techniques including applying context clues and picture clues were used to improve comprehension (Elo & Kyngäs, 2008).

Ramirez & Masariegos (2017) stated that reading comprehension is defined as the ability to understand what is read; it encompasses

the development of meanings by obtaining outstanding ideas from a text, as well as the ability to create relations. Likewise, it is also specified as a linguistic skill that allows for the interpretation of the text, requiring that a reader have attitude, experience, and foremost, knowledge (Gardunño, 2019).

Post Assessment on Phil-IRI Proficiency Level

The post-assessment was conducted after the implementation of the Contextualized Learning Kit (CLK). Given the techniques, practices, and mastery of the contents, the participants were tasked to apply the acquired learning in reading and answering the passage in the Phil-IRI tool for the post-assessment. Moreover, post-assessment is administered after an assignment, after a unit of the course, or at the end of the term in a school year to gauge what learners have learned and help them to reflect on a lesson or assignment. When joined up with a pre-assessment, a post-assessment can help trail a learner's progress over some time (Shirk, 2020).

Table 4. Post-assessment Results on Word Recognition

<i>Test Group</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Proficiency Level</i>
Experimental	90.427	5.792	Instructional
Controlled	93.415	3.844	Instructional

Note: n=40. Proficiency Level: 89 and below Frustration; 90-96 Instructional; 97-100 Independent.

Table 4 shows the post-assessment result of both the Experimental and Controlled groups on Word Recognition. Furthermore, Table 4 gives clarity on the slight difference between the Experimental and Controlled groups in the mean and standard deviation while the Phil-IRI parameters of the two (2) groups were on the Instructional Level. For this reason, the Experimental group has a mean of 90.427 with a standard deviation of 5.792 which brings the participants of this group to the Instructional Level while the Controlled group has a mean of 93.415 with a standard deviation of 3.844 that made the group remain under the Instructional level based on the parameters of Phil-IRI tool.

Hence, the data indicates that the participants belong to the Experimental group were able to enrich their proficiency level from the Frustration to the Instructional with the following parameters: three (3) of which are Independent; eight (8) of which are Instructional; and nine (9) of which remains Frustration while the participants belong to the Controlled group remains in the Instructional Level with the following parameters; five (5) are Independent, eleven (11) are Instructional, and four (4) are in Frustration. This skyrocket increase of scores in Word Recognition is the positive response of the participants from the implemented Contextualized Learning Kit (CLK) in which it allows the participants to practice, comprehend, and master the difficult terms within their grade level and understanding the concepts.

Pancare, R. (2021) noted that instructors should encourage their students to use books, images, and printed materials to decipher difficult language, forecast possible outcomes, comprehend the plot of a novel, and draw parallels between the book and other books they've read or their own life.

Tuncay, A.A. & Dedeoglu, H. (2019) revealed that in order for reading to be meaningful, students are expected to recognize the vocabulary items that exist in a text. They also added that word recognition is often used in educational applications to make reading more relevant for pupils and to discover and rectify errors.

Table 5. Post-assessment Results on Reading Comprehension

<i>Test Group</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Proficiency Level</i>
Experimental	64.286	13.513	Instructional
Controlled	78.571	15.019	Instructional

Note: n=40. Proficiency Level: 58% and below-Frustration; 59%-79% Instructional; 80%-100% Independent.

Table 5 presents the post-assessment results of the participants on Reading Comprehension for both Experimental and Controlled groups. The table shows the comparative results based on the post-assessment after the implemented Contextualized Learning Kit (CLK). Looking closely at the table, the Experimental Group has a mean of 64.286 with a standard deviation of 13.513 which made the group laid to the Instructional Level while the Controlled Group has a mean of 78.571 with a standard deviation of 15.019 which made the group remains to the Instructional level based on the parameters of the Phil-IRI tool.

The data in Table 5 indicates that most of the participants under the Experimental group were improved and have valuable learning from the Contextualize Learning Kit (CLK). The scores of the participants are increasing with the following parameters: four (4) are Independent; six (6) are Instructional; and ten (10) remains in the Frustration Level. However, the participants in the Controlled group remains in the Instructional Level but some are progressing with the following parameters: eleven (11) are Independent; six (6) are Instructional; and three (3) are in Frustration. Thus, it is also noted that consistent absenteeism and none appearance during the implementation phase of the intervention may impact the over-all potential of the participants in the reading comprehension.

Table 6 displays the comparative results between the pre- and post-assessment of Word Recognition in the Experimental Group. Moreover, table 6 unlocks variable of the study with twenty (20) participants and was interpreted using the categorical frequency, percentage scores, and Phil-IRI classification with the mean and standard deviation to clearly understand the result from the gathered data.

Table 6. Pre- and Post-assessment Results on Word Recognition (Experimental Group)

Learner	Before			After			Remarks
	Score	Oral Reading (in %)	Classification	Score	Oral Reading (in %)	Classification	
1	65	79.26	Frustration	79	96.34	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
2	68	82.92	Frustration	71	86.59	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
3	64	78.04	Frustration	69	84.15	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
4	65	79.26	Frustration	78	95.12	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
5	63	76.82	Frustration	79	96.34	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
6	70	85.36	Frustration	68	82.93	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
7	72	87.80	Frustration	67	81.71	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
8	68	82.92	Frustration	78	95.12	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
9	66	80.48	Frustration	70	85.37	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
10	65	79.26	Frustration	76	92.68	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
11	64	78.04	Frustration	80	97.56	Independent	Frustration-Independent
12	66	80.48	Frustration	71	86.59	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
13	68	82.92	Frustration	68	82.93	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
14	63	76.82	Frustration	76	92.68	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
15	70	85.36	Frustration	71	86.59	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
16	72	87.80	Frustration	80	97.56	Independent	Frustration-Independent
17	72	87.80	Frustration	69	84.15	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
18	70	85.36	Frustration	78	95.12	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
19	72	87.80	Frustration	75	91.46	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
20	68	82.92	Frustration	80	97.56	Independent	Frustration-Independent
Mean	67.550	82.371	Frustration	Mean	90.427	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
St. Dev	3.154	3.847		St. Dev	5.792		

Note: n=20. Proficiency Level: 89 and below Frustration; 90-96 Instructional; 97-100 Independent.

Table 6 displays the comparative results between the pre- and post-assessment of Word Recognition in the Experimental Group. Moreover, table 6 unlocks variable of the study with twenty (20) participants and was interpreted using the categorical frequency, percentage scores, and Phil-IRI classification with the mean and standard deviation to clearly understand the result from the gathered data.

It is noted that during the pre-assessment, the scores of the twenty (20) participants fall under the frustration level with the weighted mean of 82.371 and standard deviation of 3.847. In contrary, the post-assessment result of the participants rises steeply with the categorical frequency of the following: nine (9) for frustration, eight (8) for instructional, and three (3) for independent with the weighted mean of 90.427 and standard deviation of 5.792 and devised as Instructional Level. Moreover, looking closely at the remarks column, it is noted that eleven (11) participants were improved and nine (9) participants were remained with the success improved rate of fifty-five (55) percent based on the Proficiency Level of the Phil-IRI tool. Hence, the data uncovers the individual growth based on the effect of the Contextualized Learning Kit (CLK) to them during the implementation phase in which scores of the participants suddenly spikes. Indeed, the result doesn't much promising to all the participants, however, the data implies that the CLK is an enhancer tool that can be beneficial in the classroom and can bring significant result to the selected type of participants based on their interest, progress, and commitment to develop.

Table 7. Pre- and Post-assessment Results on Word Recognition (Controlled Group)

Learner	Before			After			Remarks
	Score	Oral Reading (in %)	Classification	Score	Oral Reading (in %)	Classification	
1	74	90.24	Instructional	77	93.90	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
2	75	91.46	Instructional	73	89.02	Frustration	Instructional-Frustration
3	74	90.24	Instructional	70	85.37	Frustration	Instructional-Frustration
4	76	92.68	Instructional	80	97.56	Independent	Instructional-Independent
5	77	93.90	Instructional	76	92.68	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
6	77	93.90	Instructional	79	96.34	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
7	76	92.68	Instructional	80	97.56	Independent	Instructional-Independent
8	78	95.12	Instructional	75	91.46	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
9	77	93.90	Instructional	76	92.68	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
10	78	95.12	Instructional	73	89.02	Frustration	Instructional-Frustration
11	76	92.68	Instructional	79	96.34	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
12	74	90.24	Instructional	81	98.78	Independent	Instructional-Independent
13	76	92.68	Instructional	80	97.56	Independent	Instructional-Independent
14	78	95.12	Instructional	73	89.02	Frustration	Instructional-Frustration
15	77	93.90	Instructional	81	98.78	Independent	Instructional-Independent
16	77	93.90	Instructional	75	91.46	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional

17	75	91.46	Instructional	75	91.46	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
18	77	93.90	Instructional	76	92.68	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
19	78	95.12	Instructional	74	90.24	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
20	75	91.46	Instructional	79	96.34	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
Mean	1.850	26.429	Frustration	Mean	64.286	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
St. Dev	0.813	11.610		St. Dev	13.513		

Note: n=20. Proficiency Level: 89 and below Frustration; 90-96 Instructional; 97-100 Independent.

Table 7 reveals the comparative results between the pre- and post-assessment of Word Recognition in the Controlled Group. Furthermore, table 7 explains the variable of the study with twenty (20) participants and was interpreted using the categorical frequency, percentage scores, and Phil-IRI classification with the mean and standard deviation to clearly understand the result from the gathered data.

On the other hand, during the pre-assessment, the scores of the twenty (20) participants fall under the instructional level with the weighted mean of 92.985 and standard deviation of 1.673 while the post-assessment result of the participants were quantified based on the categorical frequency of the following: four (4) for frustration, eleven (11) for instructional, and five (5) for independent with the weighted mean of 93.415 and standard deviation of 3.844. On the other hand, the remarks column indicated that five (5) participants were improved, eleven (1) participants were remained, and four (4) participants were downgraded with the success improved rate of only twenty-five (25) percent based on the Proficiency Level of the Phil-IRI tool. Thus, it simply shows that the post-assessment result is partially affected by the pre-assessment result. Furthermore, the data also reveals the shrinkage of scores from the post-assessment result among the participants which fall under the frustration level while other participants upturn their scores to the independent level. This phenomenon occurs due to inactive participation during the implementation while some participants opted to absent during the intervention.

Table 8. Pre- and Post-assessment Results on Reading Comprehension (Experimental Group)

Learner	Before			After			Remarks
	Score	Oral Reading (in %)	Classification	Score	Oral Reading (in %)	Classification	
1	1	14.29	Frustration	5	71.43	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
2	2	28.57	Frustration	4	57.14	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
3	2	28.57	Frustration	5	71.43	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
4	1	14.29	Frustration	4	57.14	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
5	3	42.86	Frustration	6	85.71	Independent	Frustration-Independent
6	2	28.57	Frustration	4	57.14	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
7	3	42.86	Frustration	5	71.43	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
8	3	42.86	Frustration	5	71.43	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
9	1	14.29	Frustration	5	71.43	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
10	1	14.29	Frustration	4	57.14	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
11	2	28.57	Frustration	6	85.71	Independent	Frustration-Independent
12	3	42.86	Frustration	3	42.86	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
13	2	28.57	Frustration	5	71.43	Independent	Frustration-Independent
14	1	14.29	Frustration	4	57.14	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
15	1	14.29	Frustration	6	85.71	Independent	Frustration-Independent
16	2	28.57	Frustration	4	57.14	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
17	3	42.86	Frustration	3	42.86	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
18	1	14.29	Frustration	3	42.86	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
19	2	28.57	Frustration	4	57.14	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
20	1	14.29	Frustration	5	71.43	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
Mean	1.850	26.429	Frustration	Mean	64.286	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
St. Dev	0.813	11.610		St. Dev	13.513		

Note: n=20. Proficiency Level: 58% and below-Frustration; 59%-79% Instructional; 80%-100% Independent

Table 8 exhibits the comparative results between the pre- and post-assessment of Reading Comprehension in the experimental group. Table 8 shows the variable of the study in which the data has twenty (20) participants and was interpreted using the categorical frequency, percentage scores, and Phil-IRI classification with the mean and standard deviation to draw out the result from the gathered data.

Furthermore, the data disclosed that twenty (20) participants got the scores under the frustration level with the weighted mean of 26.429 and standard deviation of 11.610 which made the participants to qualify for the study while the post-assessment result exposed the fragmented frequency scores on the following: ten (10) for frustration, six (6) for instructional, and four (4) for independent with the weighted mean of 64.286 and standard deviation of 13.513. Moreover, looking closely at the remarks column, it is noted that ten (10) participants were improved and ten (10) participants were remained with the success improved rate of fifty (50) percent based on the Proficiency Level of the Phil-IRI tool. Despite of the challenging result and development backlash of learning, the over-all result is still a hope in the implementation process for its outcome wherein the data untold towards Frustration to Instructional Level which

remains a great progress to the group of participants. This result specifies that comprehension skill is something to understand and requires multiple learning tools to achieve the expected outcomes from the participants. Furthermore, this conveys that most of the participants' scores in post-assessment result are unbelievably increases while few of the participants were experiencing deferred development compared to the pre-assessment result. This data interpretation is the positive effect of Contextualized Learning Kit (CLK) done by the researcher and continuous encouragement while the intervention phase is on process.

Table 9. Pre- and Post-assessment Results on Reading Comprehension (Controlled Group)

Learner	Before			After			Remarks
	Score	Oral Reading (in %)	Classification	Score	Oral Reading (in %)	Classification	
1	3	42.86	Frustration	5	71.43	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
2	6	85.71	Independent	7	100.00	Independent	Independent-Independent
3	5	71.43	Instructional	5	71.43	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
4	3	42.86	Frustration	6	85.71	Independent	Frustration-Independent
5	5	71.43	Instructional	4	57.14	Frustration	Instructional-Frustration
6	4	57.14	Frustration	6	85.71	Independent	Frustration-Independent
7	5	71.43	Instructional	6	85.71	Independent	Instructional-Independent
8	6	85.71	Independent	6	85.71	Independent	Independent-Independent
9	4	57.14	Frustration	6	85.71	Independent	Frustration-Independent
10	5	71.43	Instructional	5	71.43	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
11	4	57.14	Frustration	3	42.86	Frustration	Frustration-Frustration
12	3	42.86	Frustration	5	71.43	Instructional	Frustration-Instructional
13	6	85.71	Independent	7	100.00	Independent	Independent-Independent
14	4	57.14	Frustration	5	71.43	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
15	5	71.43	Instructional	4	57.14	Frustration	Instructional-Frustration
16	6	85.71	Independent	5	71.43	Instructional	Independent-Instructional
17	5	71.43	Instructional	6	85.71	Independent	Instructional-Independent
18	4	57.14	Frustration	6	85.71	Independent	Frustration-Independent
19	6	85.71	Independent	7	100.00	Independent	Independent-Independent
20	5	71.43	Instructional	6	85.71	Independent	Instructional-Independent
Mean	4.700	67.143	Instructional	Mean	78.571	Instructional	Instructional-Instructional
St. Dev	1.031	14.730		St. Dev	15.019		

Note: n=20. Proficiency Level: 58% and below-Frustration; 59%-79% Instructional; 80%-100% Independent

Table 9 presents the comparative results between the pre- and post-assessment of Reading Comprehension in the controlled group. Table 9 shows the variable of the study that has twenty (20) participants and was interpreted using the categorical frequency, percentage scores, and Phil-IRI classification with the mean and standard deviation to draw out the result from the gathered data.

In addition, the data revealed that the twenty (20) participants got the unliked scores of the following: seven (7) for frustration, eight (8) for instructional, and five (5) for independent with the weighted mean of 67.143 and standard deviation of 14.730 while the post-assessment result bring out the distinct frequency scores of the following: three (3) for frustration, six (6) for instructional, and eleven (11) for independent with the weighted mean of 78.571 and standard deviation of 15.019. Furthermore, looking closely at the remarks column, it is noted that ten (10) were improved, seven (7) were remained, and three (3) were downgraded with the success improved rate of fifty (50) percent based on the Proficiency Level of the Phil-IRI tool. Thus, the data tells that participants score remained to its normal state as there is no thorough application of the CLK in their part.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the results informed the efficacy of the strategies employed in the study since significant improvement in the word recognition and reading comprehension skills of the participants was noted. The theory on reading rope which the study was anchored on and the established hypothesis have served as a guide for the attainment of the research purpose. The efficacy of context clues and picture cues for reading ability remedies are old but gold strategies since numerous research have proved their appropriateness in improving the word recognition and reading comprehension skills of learners.

The improvement of the two skills can also be attributed to the competency and virtues of the teacher in the application of the strategies during remediation. Extending time for such purposes defines the sacrifices of a teacher to advance the reading ability of the learners. The conduct of class remediation beyond the official hour of duty is the additional work of a teacher. Indeed, it is not the strategy that works well but the utmost dedication and commitment of the teacher to help the learners learn will matter most. The employment of a strategy during remediation only aids the teacher to become effective in the delivery of instruction but her inner virtues push her to harness the efficacy of such strategy.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are introduced:

Policy. The output of the study may serve as basis for the school leaders and Division officials to develop localized policies recommending the utilization of the output of the study.

Practice of Profession. The findings and output of this study may serve as reference to other schools in the Division in improving the reading ability of key stage two learners.

Research. The technical aspects of this study can be replicated by other researchers specifically on the following related studies:

- Efficacy of Context Clues in Improving the Word Recognition Skills of Key Stage 2 Learners
- Efficacy of Picture Cues in Improving the Reading Ability of Key Stage 2 Learners
- Realities on the Reading Ability of Key Stage 2 Learners: A Multi-case Study

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